

An Exploratory study on Perception, Attitude and Acceptance of covid-19 booster dose vaccination by the general public in selected rural and urban areas in Puducherry

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ABSTRACT

An Exploratory study was conducted to explore the Perception, Attitudes and Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public in Selected Rural and Urban areas in Puducherry.

The objective of the study was to identify the level of Perception and Attitudes towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public, to explore the Acceptance of COVID-19 booster dose vaccination and its influencing factors among the General Public and associate the level of Perception, Attitudes and Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public with selected demographic variables.

Subjects and Methods: A quantitative research approach was used. An exploratory study was conducted by using a purposive sampling technique among 400 General Public was selected in Rural and Urban areas in Puducherry.

Result:The result revealed that the General Public had a Moderate Perception and Unfavourable Attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination in Rural and Urban areas. The Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public was 132 (66.0%) in Rural areas and 129 (64.5%) in Urban areas. There was a statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) between Perception, Attitude and Acceptance with selected demographic variables such as age, educational status, residence, employment status, previous history of COVID-19, having any chronic disease, self-reported health status and source of information about COVID-19 booster dose vaccine except religion.

Conclusion: The study concluded that General Public had a Moderate perception with an unfavourable attitude to accept COVID-19 booster dose vaccination in both Rural and Urban areas.

Health professionals especially community Health Nursing officers play a very important role in motivating the General Public to adopt COVID-19 booster dose vaccination and promote 100% vaccination in the Union Territory of Puducherry. The study also recommends that necessary steps should be taken by the Government and Public Health authorities to increase COVID-19 booster dose vaccination acceptance with high perception and foster a favourable attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public in Rural and Urban areas.

Keywords: Perception, Attitude, Acceptance, General Public, COVID-19 Booster dose vaccination.

1.INTRODUCTION

The current coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, one of the most catastrophic challenges to civilization since the 1918–1919 Spanish flu pandemic, is now essentially unavoidable¹. In December 2019, Wuhan City in China's Hubei Province reported the first case of COVID-19. Patients visiting the wet market, which also has certain wildlife species, were the ones who first discovered the first instances. Large epidemics have been documented ever then in other nearby nations and other Chinese provinces, eventually affecting the entire world². Due to the ongoing rise in reported cases, the World Health Organization (WHO) officially designated this epidemic a global pandemic on March 12th. Severe Acute Respiratory Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the culprit behind COVID-19 sickness (SARS-CoV-2). While governments all over the world struggle to implement a variety of prevention strategies, such as enforcing lockdowns or stepping up testing and contact tracing, one efficient way to promote the general public's health and wellbeing is through health promotion. Health promotion can include community education, risk communication carried out by organisations at various levels, and participation of locals to recognise the risk and gravity of COVID-19. Thus, the primary goal is to promote behaviour modification among the general public so that they might adopt helpful behaviours in this protracted battle against COVID-19.

The COVID-19 vaccination programme has already started in India, but many people are still not aware of the distinctions between the two vaccinations, Covaxin and Covishield. However, the results of the first phase strongly imply that both of the vaccines being administered in India are safe and effective¹⁹. Currently, the government does not allow people to choose which vaccine they wish to get. Utilizing a completely distinct technology known as the viral vector platform, Covishield was created. ChAdOx1 is a modified chimpanzee adenovirus that can deliver the COVID-19 spike protein into human cells. Although this cold virus can't really infect the recipient, it can certainly instruct the immune system to get ready to fight off similar illnesses.

Vaccines against viruses like Ebola were created using the very same method²¹. Regarding dosage, there is no distinction between the two vaccines. In the upper arm region, 0.5ml of each is delivered. But each vaccine has a different dose schedule. For Covishield vaccines, the second dose is planned 84 days or 12–16 weeks after the first dose, whereas the second dose of Covaxin is scheduled 4–6 weeks after the first dose. On April 1, the third phase, which allows those above the age of 18 to administer life-saving shots started²². The third dosage of the mRNA vaccination should be administered at least 28 days after the second dose. Creating secure vaccinations and proving their efficacy are no longer sufficient to combat a disease because vaccine reluctance is on the rise.

Vaccine hesitancy, which refers to people's general apprehension against and resistance to vaccination, has been cited as one of the most urgent concerns affecting public health not least in light of the COVID-19 epidemic²⁰.

The present study aims to explore the Perception, Attitude and Acceptance, towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination by the General Public in Rural and Urban areas.

1.1 Need for Study

Since 2020, the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has been a major public health concern. By October 2020, there were over 35 million confirmed cases of the illness, and over a million people died from it, mostly among the higher-risk demographic, which includes obese people, smokers, and people with cancer, chronic kidney disease, heart conditions, immune system compromises, sickle cell disease, and type 2 diabetes mellitus.

COVID-19 has a high economic cost that should not be understated in addition to its effects on health. The number of workforces has significantly decreased, while unemployment has increased globally. Pharmaceutical firms are now under pressure.

Globally, according to world Health Organization stated that 647,972,911 confirmed cases of COVID-19, including 6,642,832 fatalities, have been reported to WHO as of 5:07 PM CET on December 16, 2022. A total of 13,008,560,983 vaccine doses have been given as of 12 December 2022.

In India, according to world Health Organization stated that 44,675,609 confirmed cases of COVID-19 with 530,663 fatalities have been reported to WHO between 3 January 2020 and 5:07 PM CET on 16 December 2022. A total of 2,199,517,388 doses of vaccine have been given as of 5 December 2022.

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of knowledge, attitude, and practise of COVID-19 among the Public in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Yasmin et al. (2021) did a cross-sectional study. The majority of study participants had some familiarity with COVID-19. Indicating a high degree of knowledge, the mean COVID-19 knowledge score was 17.96 (SD = 2.24, range: 3-22). Positive attitudes were indicated by the mean attitude score of 28.23 (SD = 2.76, range: 6-30). The average practice score was 4.34 (SD = 0.87, range: 0-5), which is an excellent result. According to the study's findings, this susceptible demographic should receive focused health education interventions since they may be more likely to contract COVID-19. For instance, men-specific health education initiatives may result in a considerable rise in COVID-19 knowledge²⁹.

Researchers had a lot of difficulty convincing the public to adopt the covid-19 vaccine during community posts. As a result, the researcher is interested in conducting a study to examine General Public Perception, Attitudes, and Acceptance of the covid-19 booster dose vaccination in particular areas.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

A study to explore the Perception, Attitude and Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public in selected rural and urban areas in Puducherry.

1.3 Objectives

1. To identify the level of Perception and Attitudes towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public.
2. To explore the Acceptance of COVID-19 booster dose vaccination and its influencing factors among the General Public.
3. To compare the level of Perception and Attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public between Rural and Urban areas.
4. To find out the correlation between Perception and Acceptance; Perception and Attitude; Attitude and Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public
5. To associate the level of Perception, Attitudes and Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public with selected demographic variables.

2. METHODOLOGY

Explorative descriptive research design was used. 400 General Public were selected by using Purposive sampling technique. The tool includes **Section A:** Demographic variables of the General Public towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination. **Section B:** Structured Questionnaire on Perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public. **Section C:** Structured Questionnaire on Attitudes towards covid-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public. **Section D:** Structured questionnaire on Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public.

2.1 Scoring

The total questions for perception and attitude are 20 as 5 positive questions and 5 negative questions and is marked by five - point Likert scale. The positive statements were rated on 5 points-Strongly Agree-5, Agree-4, Neutral-3, Strongly Disagree-2 and Disagree-1. The maximum score for the positive statement was 5 and the negative statement was scored reversely. Thus, the total score was 50.

The obtained scores were classified into 3 levels of perception and attitude as High Perception and Favourable Attitude 31-50 **Above 75%**, Moderate Perception and Moderately Favourable Attitude 16-30 **51%-75%**, Poor Perception and Unfavourable Attitude 1-15 **≤50%**.

Acceptance towards covid-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public is assessed by using one statement with two options (Yes or No) followed by the reasons for the options chosen.

The scoring pattern was given as one mark for 'Yes' answer and Zero mark for 'No'.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Public Perception, Attitude and Acceptance of COVID-19 booster dose was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, distribution, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (chi-square test). The data was analyzed based on the objectives of the study.

The discussion of the present study is based on the findings obtained from statistical analysis and given based on the objectives of the present study.

Distribution of Demographic variables: Out of 400 samples, regarding the age majority, 208 (52%) of samples belonged to 18-26 years, 108 (27%) belonged to 27-35 years, 62 (15.5%) belonged to 36-44 years and 22 (5.5%) belonged to above 45 years of age.

Regarding Gender, the majority 191 (47.8%) were female, 204 (51.0%) were male and 5 (1.3%) were transgender.

Regarding Educational Status, the majority 170 (42.5%) were graduates, 91 (22.8%) were higher secondary, 76 (19.0%) had primary education and 63 (15.8%) were illiterate.

Regarding Residence, half of the General Public 200 (50%) reside in Rural areas and 200 (50%) residing in Urban areas.

Regarding the Religion, majority 247 (61.8%) were Hindus, 151 (37.8%) were Christians and 2 (0.5%) were Muslims.

Regarding the Employment Status, the majority 158 (39.5%) were employed, 116 (29.0%) were unemployed, 104 (24.0%) were students and 22 (5.5%) were retired from service.

Regarding the Previous History of COVID-19, the majority of 342 (85.5%) of been affected with COVID-19 previously and 58 (14.5%) did not have a previous history of COVID-19.

Regarding the History of Chronic Disease, the majority 314 (78.5%) were free from chronic diseases and 86 (21.5%) had a history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, hyperthyroidism or in combination.

Regarding Self-reported Health, the majority 282 (70.5%) had reported that they had good health status and 118 (29.5%) had reported that their health status was not stable.

Regarding the Source of Information about COVID-19 booster dose vaccination, the majority 237 (59.3%) of them had known through social media, 31 (7.8%) received awareness from health care providers and 132 (33.0%) got to know through their family members.

The **first objective** of the study is to identify the level of perception and attitude towards covid-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public between rural and urban areas. The results revealed that out of 200 samples in Rural areas, the majority **123 (61.5%)** had a moderate perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination whereas **75 (37.5%)** of them had a high perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination and only **2 (1.0%)** had poor perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination. Out of 200 samples in Urban areas, the majority **121 (60.5%)** had a moderate perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination, while the rest **79 (39.5%)** of them had a high perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination. Regarding the General Public attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination, the majority **152 (76.0%)** had unfavourable attitudes towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination while **48 (24%)** had moderately favourable attitudes towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination in the Rural area, whereas the majority **157 (78.5%)** had an unfavourable attitude while **43 (21.5%)** had a moderately favourable attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination in the Urban areas.

The Second objective of the study is to explore the acceptance of COVID-19 booster dose and its influencing factors among the General Public.

The study results revealed Out of 400 samples, 132 (66.0%) and 129(64.5%) of the General Public accepted the COVID-19 booster dose vaccination from the Rural and Urban area respectively.

Of the 400 samples, a total of 261 (65.2%) of the General Public had accepted the COVID-19 booster dose vaccination and the reasons for the acceptance of The Covid-19 Booster vaccination where as follows: most of the General Public 118(45.2%) had accepted the COVID-19 booster dose vaccination voluntarily while 76(29.1%) had accepted under the pressure of a healthcare worker and about 20(7.7%) had accepted to protect themselves from covid-19 (migrators), 16(6.13%) had accepted to gain Government benefits and 20(7.66%) had accepted out of fear of death and losing family members due to COVID-19.

In the present study, out of 400 General Public, 139 samples had not accepted the vaccination for the reason stated as 91(65.5%) of them out of fear of death and losing family members, 38 (27.3%) of them were not interested and 10(7.2%) of them were frequently infected (after receiving 2 doses of covid-19 vaccination).

The third objective of the study is to compare the level of Perception and Attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public between Rural and Urban areas. The results revealed that out of 200 samples in Rural areas, the Mean and Standard Deviation of Perception and Attitude in Rural areas was 33.98 ± 4.08 , 22.06 ± 6.88 and out of 200 samples in Urban areas, the Mean and Standard Deviation of Perception and Attitude in the Urban area was 34.35 ± 3.84 , 21.77 ± 6.67 There is no statistically significant difference between the Perception and Attitude of the General Public, thus eliciting that the Perception and Attitude of both the Rural and Urban Population was the same towards the COVID-19 booster dose vaccination.

The fourth objective of the study is to find out the Correlation between Perception and Acceptance; Perception and Attitude; Attitude and Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public.

The results revealed that the non-significant r value ($r=0.057$) at $p=0.258$ was no statistically significant correlation between Perception and Acceptance towards covid-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public.

The significant 'r-value ($r=-0.475$) at $p=0.000$ revealed that there was statistically significant correlation between the perception and attitude of the General Public in the Negative direction towards the COVID-19 Booster dose vaccination. Similarly, the significant r value ($r=-0.439$) at $p=0.000$ showed statistically significant correlation between the Attitude and Acceptance in the Negative direction.

The fifth objective of the study is to associate the level of Perception, Attitude and Acceptance towards covid-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public with selected demographic variables.

The results revealed that there was a statistically significant association between perception, attitude and acceptance with selected demographic variables such as age, educational status, residence, employment status, previous history of COVID-19 having any chronic disease, self-reported health

status and source of information about COVID-19 booster dose vaccine except religion.

It was determined to plan for data collection and analysis. Data were analysed by descriptive (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (chi-square test).

3.1 Major Findings of the Study

The demographic variables of the study as the majority of the samples 208(52%) belonged to the age group between 18-26 years, the majority 191 (47.8%) were female and the majority 170 (42.5%) were graduates, the majority 247 (61.8%) were Hindu, majority 158(39.5%) were employed and regarding the previous history of COVID-19 majority 342(85.5%) were affected by COVID-19. History of chronic disease majority 314(78.5%) was free from chronic diseases. Self-reported health status majority 282(70.5%) had good health status and regarding sources of information about COVID-19 booster dose majority of 237(59.3%) had known through social media.

Regarding the level of Perception, in Rural and Urban areas 123(61.5%),121(60.5%) General Public had Moderate Perception and 152(76%),157(78.5%) Unfavourable Attitudes towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination in Rural and Urban and most of the General Public 132 (66.0%),129 (64.5%) in rural and urban areas were accepted the COVID-19 booster dose vaccination. There is no difference between general Public Perception and Attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination between rural and urban areas ($p=0.351$, $p=0.674$). There is no significant correlation between Public Perception and Acceptance; Perception and Attitude; Attitude and Acceptance towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination.

There was a statistically significant association ($p<0.001$) between Perception, Attitude and Acceptance with selected demographic variables such as age, gender, educational status, residence, employment status, previous history of COVID-19, having any chronic disease, self-reported health status and source of information about COVID-19 booster dose vaccine except religion.

SECTION A: DISTRIBUTION OF THE SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE GENERAL PUBLIC.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage distribution of socio-demographic variables of the General Public.

N=400

Demographic Variables	Frequency No	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
18-26years	208	52.0
27-35 years	108	27.0
36-44years	62	15.5
above 45years	22	5.5

Gender		
Male	191	47.8
Female	204	51.0
Transgender	5	1.3
Educational status		
Illiterate	63	15.8
Primary	76	19.0
Hr. Sec	91	22.8
Graduates	170	42.5
Residence		
Urban	200	50.0
Rural	200	50.0
Religion		
Hindu	247	61.8
Muslim	2	0.5
Christian	151	37.8
Others	0	0.0

Employment status		
Employed	158	39.5
Retired	22	5.5
Unemployed	116	29.0
Still a student	104	26.0
Previous history of covid 19		
Yes	342	85.5
No	58	14.5
Having any chronic disease		
Yes,	86	21.5
No	314	78.5

Self-reported health status		
Good	282	70.5
Fair	118	29.5
Poor	0	0.0
10. Source of information about Covid-19 booster vaccine		
Health care provider	31	7.8
Government	0	0.0
Social media	237	59.3
Family members	132	33.0

SECTION B: Frequency and Percentage of the level of Perception and Attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public between Rural and Urban areas.

Table 2: Distribution of the frequency and percentage of the level of Perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public between Rural and Urban areas.

N = 400

Level of Perception	Rural n = 200		Urban n = 200	
	No	%	No	%
Poor Perception	2	1.0	0	0.0
Moderately Perception	123	61.5	121	60.5
High Perception	75	37.5	79	39.5

Figure 1. Distribution of the Level of Perception towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public.

Table 3: Distribution of the level of Attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public.

N= 400

Level of Attitude	Rural n = 200		Urban n = 200	
	No	%	No	%
Unfavourable attitude	152	76.0	157	78.5
Moderately Favourable attitude	48	24.0	43	21.5
Favourable Attitude	0	0.0	0	0.0

Figure 2. Distribution of the Level of Attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public.

SECTION C: Distribution of the frequency and percentage of acceptance and factors influencing acceptance of the COVID-19 Booster dose vaccine among the General Public.

Table 4: Distribution of the frequency and percentage of acceptance of the COVID-19 Booster dose vaccine among the General Public.

N=400

Variable	Rural n = 200		Urban n = 200		Total n = 400	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Acceptance	132	66.0	129	64.5	261	65.2
Total	200	100.0	200	100.0	400	100.0

Figure 3. Distribution of Acceptance of Covid-19 booster dose vaccination among the General Public.

Table 5: Frequency and percentage distribution of factors influencing Acceptance of The Covid-19 Booster dose vaccination among the General Public.

N=261

FACTORS	ACCEPTANCE	
	No.	%
Compulsion of health care worker	76	29.1
By their own willingness	118	45.2
Motivated by the government by Gaining benefits	16	6.13
Protecting themselves from covid-19 (migrators).	20	7.7
For the benefit of their family members (reduce the transmission of infection)	11	4.21
Due to fear of death /lose of their family member	20	7.66

Table 6: Frequency and percentage distribution of factors influencing Non-Acceptance of the COVID-19 Booster vaccination among the General Public.

N=139

FACTORS	Non-Acceptance N=139	
	No.	%
Due to fear death /loss of their family member	91	65.5
Not having interest	38	27.3
Getting frequent infection (after receiving 2 doses of COVID-19 vaccination)	10	7.2

4. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that General Public had a Moderate perception with an unfavourable attitude to accept COVID-19 booster dose vaccination in both Rural and Urban areas. Health professionals especially community Health Nursing officers play a very important role in motivating the General Public to adopt COVID-19 booster dose vaccination and promote 100% vaccination in the Union Territory of Puducherry. The study also recommends that necessary steps should be taken by the Government and Public Health authorities to increase COVID-19 booster dose vaccination acceptance with high perception and foster a favourable attitude towards COVID-19 booster dose vaccination among General Public in Rural and Urban areas.

ETHICAL APPROVAL AND CONSENT

Ethical clearance has been obtained from the institutional ethical committee, the Public Health Department of Puducherry, the Medical Officers of PHCs in selected areas of Puducherry, and informed consent was obtained from General Public.

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